

Training Needs Analysis For Teachers: Viewpoints Of School Heads

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Abstract. This study investigates the experiences of school principals in the training needs analysis of teachers. This study employed a phenomenological research design to determine the experiences and perceptions of the eight (8) participants. On the positive experiences, the themes generated were gaining insights into teachers' strengths and weaknesses and creating a culture of professional development. On the other hand, the themes of the negative experiences of the school principals were allocating limited training resources and time constraints. Regarding coping ways, the generated themes were fostering collaboration, utilizing different assessment techniques, and promoting internal resources. The themes generated by the educational management insights were conducting program evaluations to measure training effectiveness, involving teachers in the process, and encouraging teacher-led initiatives. The themes implied that school principals should improve their democratic leadership skills to conduct training needs analysis of teachers effectively and efficiently. Training effectiveness should be determined, and teachers should be assigned roles and responsibilities so that they can take charge of and direct their professional development. The results generated provided comprehensive data for future research with a similar scope.

KEY WORDS

1. experiences 2. coping ways 3. insights 4. training needs analysis

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1. Introduction

Training for teachers is essential to attain the required knowledge, skills, and attitudes to accomplish jobs more efficiently, given that training is the procedure for assisting them to gain further knowledge of their tasks and also to learn or improve the required skills, attitudes, and values linked to the competent performance of their work (Tulsian Pandy, 2009). In obtaining new knowledge and skills, attitudes are modified to improve competence and general job performance (Gomez-Meija et al., 2001). Teachers are the primary resource, given that all the other resources (e.g., machinery, materials, and money) exist to extend the effectiveness of the human resource. Therefore, training aims to allow teachers to exploit these resources to the best advantage (Parry, 2000). When giving training to teachers, a Training Needs Analysis (training needs analysis) helps identify performance requirements and the knowledge, skills, and abilities needed by the organization. A practical training needs analysis will help direct resources to areas of most significant demand. Given the importance of training needs analy-

sis, several research studies have revealed that school principals encounter challenges in conducting the analysis. In Saudi Arabia, Mulyata (2011) revealed that the primary obstacles to successful training need to be analyzed by school principals in the Saudi Arabian Basic Education sector, which is ineffective human resource management and favoritism concerning selecting candidates for training and development. The authors discussed that without effective Human Resource Management, the department could face serious legal, financial, and productivity issues. Meanwhile, favoritism affects the teacher's enthusiasm towards their job and professional development. These issues, ultimately, could lead to the delivery of poor-quality education to students. In Ghana, Africa, Ogba (2009) found inadequate human resource management in school principals as many teachers are untrained, and if they are trained, it does not match the needs and demands. These are some of the contributing factors to the worrying state of Ghana's educational system. World Bank (2018) report stressed that although Ghana had done well in enrollment for basic and second-cycle education, there was no corresponding improvement in the quality of education offered. Ghana ranked last amongst the 97 countries in the Global School Ranking. In the Philippines, Otayman (2013) discussed in his study that while the Philippines engages in certain aspects of Training and Development management, significant deficiencies remain in training needs analysis, which is a primary element to determine who needs to be trained, where training is needed and what training needs to be conducted. Otayman (2013) claimed that the country faces questions regarding properly utilizing the education budget for teacher growth and development. The Commission on Audit has flagged the Department of Education over deficiencies in utilizing funds amounting to billions of pesos. In the research locale, Matanao I, Division of Davao

del Sur, the school principals shared that they receive insufficient training and seminars in human resource management, particularly in training needs analysis. Hence, they do not have adequate human resource techniques for their school organization. Like teachers, school principals need constant training to acquire knowledge and skills in management and to remain focused on providing helpful learning opportunities for teachers. The lack of professional development for school principals, practical training needs analysis processes and techniques, and appropriate values and behaviors in conducting training needs analysis are enemies to successful teacher growth and excellence in education. The ideal situation should be that school principals are competitive in the process and should have embodied appropriate values and behaviors to effectively manage the organization's important resource—teachers. A search through the literature has shown vast studies regarding human resource management. However, few studies focus on school principals' challenges in conducting training needs analysis. Moreover, no study has been carried out on the coping strategies of school principals regarding this matter. Therefore, the challenges have not been adequately addressed up until now, and there is a big possibility that higher education institutions are not aware of the challenges. This is the gap this study is set to cover.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The study aimed to investigate the challenges of school principals in the training needs analysis for teachers and how school principals cope with the challenges. In a profession where educational excellence is a must, competency in analyzing the training needs of the teachers must align knowledge, skills, and values to the changing needs of the students and standards of the economy. Teachers need not only to be given regular training opportunities to provide good quality education, but it should also be appropriate and valuable to them. Therefore, it is

important to understand school principals' challenges in training needs analysis so teachers can provide appropriate solutions or interventions to their problems. If the challenges are addressed, the educational sector is confident that teachers receive quality training opportunities from the school principal.

1.2. *Research Questions*—The study intended to gain insight from the training needs

- (1) What are the experiences of school principals in conducting Training Needs Analysis for teachers?
- (2) How do they cope with the challenges of conducting Training Needs Analysis for teachers?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the study?

This study is significant as it offers additional research that may indicate appropriate means of making teachers feel valued. Administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders can utilize this study's findings to develop strategies to elevate school principals' competency in managing human resources, particularly in analyzing training needs. This study would be significant to the following: DepEd Officials. The study's findings would shed light on policy makers' need to give school principals training opportunities to gain sufficient knowledge and skills in analyzing teachers' training needs. The coping strategies revealed in this study would help them create a policy with guidelines on properly conducting training needs analysis. Uniformity would help school principals to have standards for analysis. School Administrators. The study's findings would shed light on possible challenges that they may encounter in training needs analysis for teachers. This study may also give them ideas on how to deal with the processes of training needs analysis properly and effectively. Teachers. The study would be meaningful as the findings may help them understand the importance of training needs analysis and how school principals analyze and utilize the results for their professional growth. They may be motivated and satisfied with their jobs since

analysis for teachers into the viewpoints Of School Heads. I wanted to narrow down the highlights and lowlights of their experiences, the challenges, and the School Heads' coping practices on the challenges that come along the way. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following:

the administration addresses their needs. Stakeholders. The findings generated may present stakeholders with ways to help the schools analyze the training needs of the teachers. They could also assist in finding resource persons or speakers for teacher training and seminars. Future Researchers. The findings provided comprehensive data for future research with similar or relevant scope.

The following term was defined for use in this study: Training Needs Analysis- also known as Training Needs Assessment, is a process that organizations use to determine the gap between the current and desired knowledge, skills, and abilities of employees.

1.3. *Review of Significant Literature*—This section presents a synthesis of literature on training, training needs analysis, benefits, methods, and the role of school principals in training assessments.

1.3.1. *Training and Professional Development*—Training enhances employees' knowledge, skills, and attitudes for improved job performance (Tulsian Pandey, 2009; Gómez-Mejía et al., 2001). Employees are key resources in organizations, and effective training fosters their ability to utilize resources efficiently (Parry, 2000). Professional development significantly influences student learning

outcomes (Hammond, 2017 as cited by Corpuz, 2019). A well-structured training evaluation process, including focus group discussions and classroom observations, enhances effectiveness (Reilly, 2016). Training contributes to organizational performance, sustainable competitive advantage, and human capital development (Armstrong, 2011; Schuller, 2000; Khadakdar Sharma, 2005). However, training programs should align with organizational objectives rather than be mere incentives (Brown, 2002). Training and development support an integrated performance system within organizations (Doughty Romiszowski, 2000).

1.3.2. Training Needs Analysis (TNA)—TNA systematically identifies required training and implementation details (Corsel, 2013). From an HR perspective, learning needs analysis bridges skill gaps and supports continuous learning (Kercher, 2000). Liberman (2005) outlined TNA's four key steps: performance gap analysis, root cause analysis, needs analysis, and recommendations. TNA ensures training aligns with organizational goals, highlights unconsidered training areas, and prioritizes critical skills development (Thyers, 2004; Sullivan et al., 2010; Odehal et al., 2013; Merton, 2011; Meyer, 2014). Proper TNA prevents resource wastage and ensures targeted training participation (Bandon, 2015; McLaney et al., 2011; Mack, 2005; Maxfield, 2012).

1.3.3. Needs Analysis Methods—Needs analysis employs various methods, including organizational documents, surveys, focus groups, individual interviews, advisory committees, workplace observations, benchmarking, and independent research (Rosset, 2000; Steadham, 2003; MyCoy, 2000). These approaches provide valuable insights but vary in involvement, cost, and effectiveness. Multiple assessment techniques ensure comprehensive training analysis (Blanchard Thacker, 2013).

1.3.4. Instructional Systems Design and ADDIE Model—Training effectiveness relies on

structured instructional systems design (ISD), which ensures quality training aligned with organizational needs (Brinkerhoff Gill, 2000). The ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation) is widely used in training design (Clark, 1995). Proper evaluation, including formative and summative assessments, refines training effectiveness (Clark, 1998).

1.3.5. School Principals' Role in Training Needs Analysis—School principals ensure training aligns with school improvement goals and teacher performance standards (McGhee, 2011). TNA occurs at organizational, operational, and individual levels, using data sources such as performance appraisals, job descriptions, and student achievement records. Limited budgets and time constraints challenge principals in implementing TNA (Smilber, 2011; Swanson, 2009; Matilda, 2011; Stephen Jones, 2011). However, strategic planning, collaboration, and proper assessment methods enhance effectiveness (Berkey, 2013).

1.3.6. Experiences and Coping Strategies of School Principals—Understanding teachers' strengths and weaknesses aids recruitment, retention, and performance improvement (Bowra et al., 2011; Khan, 2010). Training assessments support professional development, resource allocation, and time management (Griswold Boone, 2018; Smilber, 2011). Collaboration fosters effective training programs (Sims, 2002; Schein, 2010). Utilizing various assessment techniques tailors training to teachers' needs (Pan, 2008; Blanchard Thacker, 2013). Internal training resources enhance engagement and skill development (Ribeiro, 2020).

1.3.7. Educational Management Insights—Program evaluations measure training effectiveness through assessments, feedback surveys, and focus groups. Training enhances employees' skills, job performance, and motivation (Commercemates, 2022; Market Business News, 2023). Employee development im-

proves organizational performance and productivity (Kassaw, 2022). Teachers play a central role in education management, influencing student engagement and classroom effectiveness (Trevethan, 2017; Holzberger Prestele, 2021; Gröschner et al., 2018). Involving teachers in training assessments improves educational outcomes (Franklin Harrington, 2019; Sun, 2015; Aglazor, 2017). Proper class management enhances learning experiences (Putri et al., 2019). Principals using structured program evaluations ensure effective teacher training and professional development strategies.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on the Human Capital Theory proposed by Schultz in 1961 and later developed extensively by Becker (1964). The theory is based on classical growth, learning, and labor market theories. The theory states that employees are the main asset of the organization. Human capital investment has developed in the past years. This investment helps increase the worker and the organization's quality; this is why training is considered an important constituent of human productivity. Human beings are often considered the leading resource or capital of an organization. Training and development are the most important constituents of human resources that help increase organizational performance (Bowra et al., 2011). The main goal and aim of the training are to increase the organization's efficiency (Tharenou, Alan Celia, 2007). According to Aguinis Kraiger (2009), organizations' overall efficiency, profitability, and productivity are improved by training. Employee's capacity to perform well in the organization and their motivation level is increased with the help of training and development (Boxall Purcell, 2008). According to Kennedy J. 2009 through training, the organization gets a competitive advantage because the workers become more committed and more productive toward the organization. Further, according to Chris Amisano (2010), the success of an organization is dependent on

employee performance, and training is the only method through which the employees become more competent. The task becomes easier for employees, who can see a clear path toward their goals (Khan, 2010). In this competitive world, an organization must train its employees to make them more resourceful and innovative to sustain in the market. Another theory related to training needs analysis is the Motivation theory of Herzberg (1950). The theory studies understanding what drives a person to work towards a particular goal or outcome. It is relevant to management because a motivated employee is more productive, and a more productive employee is more profitable. Colman (2012) explained in his study that as training is more frequent, the motivation scores increase; less training equates to lower motivation. There is a strong correlation between the frequency of training received and the level of motivation. Moreover, Miner (2017) discussed that training can improve work quality and outcomes. As a result, employees feel happier in their work, become more excited about the prospect of success, and develop a higher self-worth. Moreover, this study is anchored on Fayol's Organization Behavior Theory (1900). The theory refers to a set of interrelated concepts that explain the behavior of individuals, groups, and subgroups who interact with each other to perform activities intended to accomplish a common goal. Fayol (1900) stressed that the theory helps explain how management behaviors and structures can positively or negatively influence employee behavior. Relating the theory to training, Barnard (1900) explains that the theory helps organizations examine the knowledge and skills employees should acquire to be efficient and motivated at work. If organizational leaders positively cater to the needs of the employees, the employees will behave positively and perform excellently in their jobs. Training needs assessment is essential because it signifies identifying the performance requirements the

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

teachers need in combination with the knowledge, skills, and abilities yet to be achieved. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) experiences of school principals in con-

ducting training needs analysis for teachers, (2) coping ways with the challenges of conducting training needs analysis for teachers, and (3) educational management insights drawn from the study which their intersection was considered as a common denominator.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. As elaborated in this chapter, exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It established the background for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types, as elaborated below. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those

of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. This study explored the challenges of school principals in conducting training needs analysis for teachers. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study pro-

gressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself and the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' This study is intended to gather information from the school principals who conduct training needs analyses for teachers. The researcher followed the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). It was assured that close interaction with the participants was established to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) argues that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using a personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. The researcher used the first person in the study to understand how stakeholders' partnerships in school-initiated programs were built and maintained between schools and the surrounding community.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology is different from the method. The

methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). This study explored the lived experiences and perspectives of the school principals in conducting training needs analysis for teachers, particularly those school principals from Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. The researchers wanted to know the deeper meaning of their experiences, which became the basis for doing qualitative research. It is a means that helps look for meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers so that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge; this experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge. We can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research de-

sign since it focused on the challenges of school principals in conducting training needs analysis for teachers. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that qualitative research primarily uses interviews. Interviews occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews were helpful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as investigating their responses further. In this qualitative research, interviews were used to explore the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in con-

ducting interviews is to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on Quad's (2016) statements, the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after the interview. Interviews were beneficial for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via extended interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was challenging. The researcher needed to decide how and when his or her observations would be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were a powerful tool for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assump-

tions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore and assess the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and the perspectives of the school principals, the researcher intended to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to the aims of the research, impart authentic knowledge and truth, and prevent errors.

Social Value – Research is essential to the society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was conducted explicitly among the elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the researcher's interest is the challenges the teachers face in using interactive media instruction in the classroom to ameliorate teaching competence.

Informed Consent – In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillierin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was

required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The informed consent letter aims to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating.

Vulnerability of Research Participants – This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety – The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered conveniently. The dominant concern of this study is the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information – This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced

back to their actual sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered, so the researcher and the respondents had no conflicts of interest. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided.

Justice – The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to answer the survey questions honestly and that any type of communication-related to the research should be done honestly. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study's results.

Transparency – The study's results were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and was placed on CD or other storage devices, which the researcher can request to provide. In addition, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process. They can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview. This allowed the participants to amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

Qualification of the Researcher – The researcher ensured that he or she was qualified to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before

writing the thesis, the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study reached its completion.

Adequacy of Facilities – The researcher strived to complete the study successfully within the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations. The researcher also ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time. **Community Involvement.** The researcher respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher expressed great pleasure in the interviewees' wholehearted participation in the study. **Plagiarism and Fabrication** as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else had said his or her way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present when working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included or that conclusions were purposefully put forward that were not accurate.

2.5. Research Participants—The participants of this study will be the 8 Principals of Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) they must be in the present position for at least 5 years- regardless of their age, sex, and marital status; and (2) they must gain a very satisfactory rating in their OPCRF. The researcher utilized the purposive

sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.6. *Research Instrument*—In gathering data, the researcher utilized an in-depth interview questionnaire. The researcher developed the interview questionnaire, which was answered by the participants orally. These researcher-made interview questionnaires were developed upon consultation and validation by the experts and underwent several processes to accommodate their suggestions. The components to be validated include the language and the conceptual levels of questions if suited to the participant's level of understanding, the suitability of the items to the research design in which there should be no leading questions, and the alignment of the interview questions to the objective of the study. The researcher is responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge to benefit educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher interviews the participants and guides them in the process. To avoid the intrusion of bias, the researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's knowledge, thoughts, and feelings. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and The-

matic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensured different ways of recording what was said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher were secured adequately as they contained sensitive information and were relevant to the research. However, the data were being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was safeguarding participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of data. The researcher saw the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensured that the findings were accurate to the participants and that their voices were heard. The researcher organized and presented the data, describing the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The study's findings were also presented by research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gave future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. *Data Collection*—To ensure safe educational continuity admits the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings to implement non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission

from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were then categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gath-

ered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a significant idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding is also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a data reduction method; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes is a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature. The researcher made sure that the school principals' experiences in conducting training needs analysis were presented comprehensively.

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the

gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a significant idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding is also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis. It involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a data reduction method; it is also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all

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The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involves analyzing the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in interpreting the data set. At this point, the researcher is cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: "defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies" (Ritchie Spencer, 1994, p. 186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations reflect the participants. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echoed the participants' actual attitudes, beliefs, and values. Figure 2 shows the steps in the study's analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness, which consists of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility involves establishing that the research findings are credible or believable from the participant's perspective. Observing the attributes of prolonged engagement, where credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the credibility issue, the researcher interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Meanwhile, transferability is the degree to which the findings can be generalized or transferred to other contexts. In this, the researcher did a thorough job of describing the relevant research context and assumptions. On the other hand, depend-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

ability is the consistency and repeatability of the research. The researcher ensured that the study's findings were evaluated by the participants and scrutinized by an external reviewer. Lastly, conformability is the degree to which findings could be confirmed or corroborated by other researchers. The researcher documented the procedures and rechecked the data during the entire research process. The researcher also ensured that the findings were free from bias.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the study's results concerning its aim. It also discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The results present the description and background of the participants assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Experiences of School Principals in Conducting Training Needs Analysis of Teachers—Training is an essential aspect of the education system, ensuring that teachers remain informed, skilled, and effective in their practice. As part of this, identifying the needs of teachers through conducting training needs analysis (TNA) is critical in planning and developing effective training programs. School principals play a crucial role in conducting TNA, and they can experience positive or negative experiences for them. The responses of the participants were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on what came from informants' accounts and reflections.

3.1.1. Positive Experiences—Gaining insights on teachers' strengths and weaknesses. Conducting TNA allows principals to gain insights into the strengths and weaknesses of their teaching staff. With this information, the principal can develop customized training programs to address the identified needs, ultimately improving the quality of instruction in the school. The participants stressed that when teachers are provided with training programs that are tailored to their strengths and weaknesses, they are more likely to engage in the training and see a positive impact on their teaching practices. This process promotes a culture of continuous improvement, which is essential for any successful organization, including schools. One of the main benefits of assessing teachers' strengths and weaknesses is to provide feedback and support to help them develop professionally. Effective feedback allows teachers to reflect on their performance and receive guidance on areas that need improvement. Moreover, according to the participants, understanding the strengths and weaknesses of teachers helps in the effective allocation of resources. Also, teachers who excel in certain areas of teaching can be assigned to mentor their peers or take on leadership roles, which can aid in the school's progress. According to Bowra et al. (2011), knowing teachers' strengths and weaknesses can help in making informed decisions about recruitment, retention, and promotion. It helps in identifying the qualities that make an effective teacher and the areas where the school needs improvement. For instance, if a school administrator is aware that they lack qualified teachers in a particular subject area, they can prioritize hiring teachers who specialize in that area. Understanding teachers' strengths and weaknesses can help improve school performance. If schools strive to hire and retain high-performing teachers and provide them with the necessary support and resources, the quality of education provided to students can be improved. This can lead to higher student achievement and better academic outcomes (Khan, 2010). In conclusion, gaining insights on the strengths and weaknesses of teachers is important to improve the quality of education.

By providing teachers with feedback and support, allocating resources effectively, making informed decisions about recruitment, promoting teachers, and improving school performance, students can receive a better learning experience. Therefore, schools should prioritize this aspect of teacher management to produce successful student outcomes. Creating a culture of professional development. The role of a principal is crucial in creating and maintaining a school culture that promotes the professional development of teachers. A significant way in which principals can achieve this is by conducting training needs analysis. Results from the needs assessment create a tailored training program; the participants asserted that this training would be significant to the teachers because it provides an opportunity to interact with them, making teachers feel involved in the process. This corroborates with Mycoy (2000), who asserted that teachers with opportunities to develop their skills are more likely to feel valued and supported in their work. This can result in improved job satisfaction, motivation, and retention rates. In turn, this helps to create a continuous improvement culture where teachers continually strive to improve their teaching practices to benefit their students. Furthermore, the participants voiced that through training needs analysis, they can encourage teachers to reflect on their teaching practices and seek feedback from their colleagues and students. By making themselves aware of their needs through reflection, they will be more encouraged to improve through attendance and participation in the training sessions tailored to them. In their article, Griswold, D. E., Boone, R. (2018) explore how training needs assessments can support teacher professional development in human resources education. The authors argue that by identifying the training needs of teachers, professional development programs that are relevant and meaningful to their work can be developed, leading to improved job performance, greater job sat-

isfaction, and a greater chance of self-drive toward professional growth. These sources highlight the importance of needs assessments in creating a culture of professional development among teachers. By identifying teachers' specific needs and tailoring professional development programs to address them, schools can support their teachers' ongoing growth and development, leading to improved teaching practices, professional growth, and better student outcomes.

3.1.2. Negative Experiences—Allocating limited training resources. The principal participants face challenges in prioritizing training needs. Once data has been gathered, principals may find that there are multiple areas where teachers require additional support. However, they may have limited resources and must prioritize which areas to address first. This task can be difficult, as all areas may be equally important. The participants further expressed that there are times that teachers may require training in areas that are expensive to deliver, such as specialized technology or advanced teaching methods. These limited resources can also lead to limited access to training materials and resources. Teachers may require access to training materials, such as textbooks, online resources, or training videos, to support their learning, making it more difficult for teachers to engage in professional development. Part of increasing the effectiveness of training programs is allocating training resources and budgets properly. According to Smilber (2011), budget is a significant consideration in analyzing and developing teacher training plans. This is hard for school principals, especially those in small schools. Small schools tend to have fewer budgets and resources compared to big schools. School principals reported that they have to cater to the varying training needs of their teachers, but they do not have an efficient budget to implement all the necessary training. This was supported by Swanson (2009), who states that budget can sig-

nificantly impact teacher training satisfaction. When teachers feel like their resources and budget for training are enough, this could lead to their motivation to join and learn from training. Time constraint. Conducting a training needs assessment is a time-consuming process. It requires school principals to collect teacher performance data, analyze it, and identify areas where additional support is needed. Additionally, administrators must consult with teachers and other stakeholders to develop effective training programs that meet the identified needs. All of these activities require significant time and effort to complete. The participants clarified that it is not only the school head who has limited time but also the teachers. It is tough for them to fit in with the schedule of the teachers since they are also dealing with numerous workloads. Time constraints can lead to a lack of accurate data. When administrators are pressured to complete the training needs assessment quickly, they may not have enough time to collect accurate and reliable data. This can result in incomplete or inaccurate information, which may lead to ineffective training programs that do not meet the needs of teachers. This corroborates with the study of Johnson Nabb (2015), who found that time constraints are a significant challenge in the needs assessment process, as they limit the amount of data that can be collected and analyzed. When administrators are

On the other hand, the themes of participants' negative experiences were allocating limited training resources and time constraints. These themes implied that training needs assessment can help build trust, transparency, and a sense of shared responsibility among teachers and administrators, leading to more effective collaboration and communication. Also, ineffective use of time and resources may lead to missed opportunities and a lack of progress in addressing teachers' needs, affecting student

pressured to complete the training needs assessment quickly, they may not have enough time to adequately consult with teachers and other stakeholders to address their needs. The authors suggest that addressing time constraints requires careful planning and management to ensure data collection and analysis are completed within the given timeframe. Mathilda (2011) asserted that it is challenging for school principals to identify knowledge gaps before they become problematic. One reason discussed by the author is time constraints. Stephen and Jones (2011) supported the study by claiming that time may be a massive obstacle that school principals face regarding training needs analysis because it may take some time to set it up correctly. Berkey (2013) emphasized that the time investment will be well worth it. The first-time school principals to conduct training needs analysis will probably be the most time-consuming, as the more they do the process, the more efficient they will become, and soon, it will just be a part of their yearly school improvement planning. Figure 3 shows the emerging themes on the experiences of school principals in conducting training needs analysis of teachers. The themes of the positive experiences were gaining insights into teachers' strengths and weaknesses and creating a culture of professional development.

outcomes.

3.2. Coping with the Challenges of Conducting Training Needs Analysis for Teachers—Conducting a teacher training needs analysis can be challenging, but it is essential in developing an effective teacher training program. The participants shared their coping strategies for conducting training needs analysis. Their responses were narrowed down into one to generate themes and subthemes. These were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants'

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Experiences of School Principals in Conducting Training Needs Analysis of Teachers

accounts and reflections.

3.2.1. Fostering collaboration—Collaboration between school principals and teachers is essential for analyzing practical training needs. It allows trainers to understand the needs and expectations of teachers while designing training programs to improve their competencies. According to the participants, a collaborative approach can bridge the gap between principals and teachers, resulting in mutual understanding, improved communication, and better-designed training programs. For the participants, by working together, school principals and teachers can identify the learning objectives relevant to the teachers' job roles, which can help them acquire essential skills and knowledge required for effective teaching. Another benefit of fostering collaboration among the participants is that it helps increase teachers' participation and engagement. When trainers involve teachers in training needs analysis, they become more invested in the training programs. This corroborates with Corsel (2013), who states that fostering collaboration with teachers leads to a greater sense of ownership and accountability for the teachers, which results in better outcomes from the training programs. Collaboration also helps to create a culture of continuous improvement. The feedback and ideas teachers share can help trainers refine their training programs to meet the changing needs of the education sector. This approach can help trainers to be more responsive to the needs of teachers, which can lead to a more effective and efficient training program. Collaboration improves the way the organization works together and solves problems. This leads to more innovation, efficient processes, increased success, and improved communication. Sims (2002) explained that school principals should be able to secure the cooperation of teachers in order for collaboration to happen. School principals should have the expertise and performance consulting skills necessary to be considered partners by teachers in their profes-

sional growth. Schein (2010) also noted that school principals should be willing to listen and learn from their teachers to gauge their needs and interests and to gain essential feedback for the development and improvement of training.

3.2.2. Utilizing different assessment techniques—To conduct a practical training needs analysis, school principals should use different methods to comprehensively understand their teachers' needs. According to the participants, there are varying techniques that they can use to identify the needs of the teachers, such as classroom observations, interviews, focus group discussions, and questionnaires. If chosen wisely, these techniques will help the school principals acquire the data amidst the challenge of limited time due to varying work. Furthermore, the participants shared that one advantage of using different methods in conducting training needs analysis is that each method provides a unique perspective on teachers' needs. In addition, the participants asserted that when there is time, interviews can be conducted to gather detailed information about an individual's training needs. This method is time-consuming but can provide valuable insights into an employee's strengths and weaknesses. School principals can comprehensively understand their teachers' needs using different methods and tailor training programs accordingly. School principals can identify common areas of need by gathering data from multiple sources and developing training programs that address these needs. This can help ensure that teachers are engaged in the training and that it is helpful. It can also help ensure that training programs are tailored to individual teachers' needs rather than providing a one-size-fits-all approach (Pan, 2008). Blanchard and Thacker (2013) emphasize the importance of using multiple methods to assess training needs. This can help school principals identify a broad range of training needs, ensure that training programs are relevant and effective, and identify areas where additional training may be necessary.

3.2.3. *Promoting internal resources*—Organizations can maximize their limited resources by utilizing internal resources such as trainers, coaches, and subject matter experts who are already within the organization. This will not only save costs but also enable the organization to tap into existing expertise and knowledge. According to the participants that the best trainers for training programs may already be among the employees. Turning teachers into trainers can lead to a better learning experience and may even drive stronger knowledge transfer within the team. This corroborates with Holton and Naquin (2009), who asserted that one of the main advantages of utilizing internal resources for training is that it can save costs. Hiring external trainers or consultants can be expensive, and organizations with limited budgets may struggle to afford them. Organizations can save on costs by using internal resources while ensuring their employees receive quality training. Moreover, the participants voiced that another benefit of utilizing internal resources for training is that it can promote knowledge-sharing and collaboration within the organization. Internal trainers or subject matter experts deeply understand the organization's culture, goals, and values and can impart this knowledge to employees during training. This can help build employees' shared sense of purpose and identity, improving teamwork and collaboration. They also claimed that when the team brings its expertise to the table, everyone can coach each other, teach new skills, and elevate the team as a whole. Every good team has a diversity of knowledge that will contribute to new approaches to achieving success.

3.3. *Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experiences of School Principals*—Educational management insights derived from school principals' experiences conducting teacher training needs analyses are re-

vealed and narrowed into themes. Collaboration improves the way the team works together and problem-solves. This leads to more innovation, efficient processes, increased success, and improved communication. Through listening to and learning from team members, they can help each other reach their goals. It takes hard work and a small quantity of time, but collaboration is worth it for the benefits the team will gain. A team that knows how to collaborate is comfortable sharing their ideas and adding new processes and tools. That level of participation means teammates can communicate with each other clearly and directly. This brings innovations and ways the team can improve (Ribeiro, 2020). A supported employee is a satisfied employee who is comfortable sharing expertise and aligned with team goals but is prepared to tackle what is next. Moreover, a satisfied team member comes in each day ready to work and help the rest of the team. Engagement is important for many workplace benefits, such as productivity, profitability, retention, and happiness, to name a few. As more workplaces prioritize employee engagement as a metric for success, it's essential to foster a collaborative environment by becoming a training resource for better engagement (Ribeiro, 2020). Figure 4 shows the emerging themes on coping with the challenges of conducting training needs analysis for teachers: fostering collaboration, utilizing different assessment techniques, and promoting internal resources. These themes implied that by adopting these practices, organizations could develop more effective, practical, and relevant training programs, build a continuous learning and development culture, and demonstrate their commitment to investing in their employees.

vealed and narrowed into themes.

3.3.1. *Conducting program evaluations to measure training effectiveness*—The study participants discussed that program evaluation can be used to measure the effectiveness of train-

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes on the Coping with the Challenges of Conducting Training Needs Analysis for Teachers

ing given. Through it, the school principals can collect and analyze data to determine whether the training meets its intended goals and objectives, identify strengths and weaknesses, and gain recommendations for improvement. The study participants implied that program evaluation is a must to have an objective and accurate understanding of what works and what does not work in the training. This information can be used to make informed decisions about whether to continue, expand, or discontinue the training and to allocate resources effectively. The participant stressed that program evaluation results can help identify areas of strength and weakness in training and provide recommendations for improvement. The participant suggested sustainability in the training program. The program's sustainability may happen if school principals identify the factors contributing to its success. Evaluation results can help ensure its sustainability over time. This also includes identifying the resources and partnerships needed to support the training activities and achieve its goals. The participants' insights on conducting program evaluations to measure training effectiveness are linked to the utilization-focused evaluation of Patton (2002). The author stated that a program evaluation can help determine whether the training meets its objectives and whether the participants are acquiring the intended knowledge and skills. This information can be used to identify areas for improvement in the training content, delivery method, and materials. Furthermore, Patton (2002) discussed that by analyzing the data from the evaluation, the trainers can determine what parts of the training participants are struggling with and what improvements can be made to make the training more effective and efficient for them. Moreover, Wholey, Hatry, and Newcomer's (2010) study is another one in which the participants' perceptions are related. According to the authors, school principals must gain insights into the individual needs of their teachers during training.

They should be able to adjust the training content, pace, and delivery to meet the teachers' specific needs and provide them with objective and appropriate feedback. The feedback may improve teachers' professional development, increase students' learning, develop teacher accountability, and improve teacher morale and school principal-teacher communication.

3.3.2. *Involving teachers in the process—*

Teachers are the ones who are acquiring training and programs for development. They have first-hand experience with the course and materials and can provide helpful feedback on its effectiveness. Moreover, increased teacher involvement in school decision-making is important for improving the quality of decisions in school operations (Somech, 2010). The participants implied that involving teachers in training needs analysis can help ensure that training is practical and relevant, improve the quality of education, and inform future planning and development. Involving teachers in the process can be done through surveys, focus groups, or one-on-one interviews. They may have unique needs based on their subject area, grade level, or teaching style that the school principal is unaware of. The participant expressed that involving teachers in school processes through sharing leadership can increase collaboration, improve the quality of the teaching-learning process, and build a sense of ownership and involvement among the teachers. In addition, it encourages open lines of communication in school, making it easier for teachers to talk about their thoughts and concerns to the school principal. A culture that encourages open communication is one way to help guarantee that different points of view are heard and respected in school decision-making processes. The insights on involving teachers in training needs analysis relate to the study of Orrill (2006), who states that shared leadership with the teachers in analyzing training needs is important in achieving effective educational policies in school. Keeping teachers abreast of

the process enhances their participation, honesty, and support in professional development programs in school. Moreover, it increases their morale, professional efficiency, ability, and knowledge to meet their needs and perform better. Further, Kozma (2003) also noted in his study that teacher involvement in training needs analysis keeps teachers motivated, boosts their self-efficacy, and makes them more dedicated to their duties. Moreover, Corpuz (2013) mentioned in his research article that teachers will strive more to be helpful to the school when they think that they are given importance and that their opinions are valued. School principals who participate in the decisions to contribute to the school's professional development program and the teachers are more successful. Leadership should be re-considered, re-evaluated, and re-interpreted for today's organizations. An understanding of making cooperative decisions based on a mutual understanding should be adopted in educational organizations rather than the leadership of a single person (Drossel Eickelmann, 2017).

3.3.3. Encouraging teacher-led initiatives—The most effective method for empowering teachers to become self-directed is to provide them with opportunities to implement initiatives in the school. Encouraging and supporting teacher-led initiatives can help to foster a culture of innovations within the school. Teachers empowered to pursue their own ideas and projects are more likely to take risks and try new things, which can lead to positive changes in teaching and learning. The participant implied that being self-directed encourages teachers to become lifelong learners, constantly seeking new knowledge and skills to improve their teaching practices. It is in everyone's best interest if it is not the school principal but rather the teachers who are the ones who reflect on their practices, determine their areas for improvement, and formulate plans for their personal development. The school principal would be their learning and

development facilitator and manager. Based on the response, the participant implied that working as a team can lead to improved problem-solving, increased efficiency, enhanced innovation, improved communication, support and motivation, enhanced learning, and increased accountability. These benefits can lead to improved job performance and job satisfaction and help create a positive work environment. Teamwork is important for achieving common goals. By working as a team, rather than the school principal working alone, the school principal and teachers can address more needs than they would be able to address alone and create a positive and productive work environment. The participants' insights concurred with the study of Carle, Jaffee, and Miller (2009) that encouraging teacher-led initiatives fosters self-directed teachers. Self-directed teachers could demonstrate a high degree of awareness regarding their responsibility for meaningful learning and can monitor their professional growth. Also, in the research article of Mizell (2010), encouraging teacher-led initiatives enables teachers to arouse their interest and learning initiative, improve professional learning effectiveness, and develop teachers' Autonomous professional learning capacity. Furthermore, teacher-led initiatives, such as inviting and gathering stakeholders and identifying problems and solutions, trigger reforms or change in the educational institution to meet the contemporary demand of the 21st-century teaching-learning process. School principal has a critical role to play in encouraging teachers to initiate and facilitate change in school and satisfy the national labor requirement and economic demand (O'Reilly, 2016). Figure 5 shows the emerging themes of the educational management insights drawn from the experiences of school principals. The themes were conducting program evaluation to measure training effectiveness, involving teachers in the process, and encouraging teacher-led initiatives. The themes implied that school prin-

Fig. 5. Enter Caption

principals should conduct training needs analysis in order for them to take ownership, direction, with a democratic approach. The efficacy of and responsibility for their professional development. the training should be determined, and teachers should be assigned roles and responsibilities

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study and its implications based on its findings. Future directions in school principals’ experiences were also discussed here.

4.1. Implications—This study aimed to investigate the experiences of school principals in conducting training needs analyses for teachers. The positive experiences generated included gaining insights into teachers’ strengths and weaknesses and creating a culture of professional development.

4.1.1. Gaining insights into teachers’ strengths and weaknesses—Every teacher possesses unique skills and experiences that contribute to their effectiveness in the classroom. Identifying teachers’ strengths enables educa-

tional institutions to leverage these capabilities and create opportunities for them to share their expertise with their peers. Strengths can include effective classroom management, subject knowledge, creativity, or the ability to engage students. Recognizing and celebrating these strengths boosts teacher morale and enhances collaboration within the teaching community.

4.1.2. Creating a culture of professional development—Promoting teacher collaboration encourages the exchange of best practices and facilitates peer learning. Platforms for shar-

ing ideas and experiences, such as professional learning communities or mentorship programs, can be established. These positive experiences implied the need to develop tailored professional development programs based on the identified training needs. Educational institutions can design targeted professional development programs that are interactive, collaborative, and aligned with teachers' goals and objectives. On the other hand, the themes of the school principals' negative experiences were allocating limited training resources and time constraints.

4.1.3. Allocating limited training resources—Educational institutions typically have finite resources for teacher training, including financial, human, and material assets. It is essential to prioritize and allocate these resources strategically to maximize their impact. By conducting a needs assessment, institutions can identify the areas where training is most needed, enabling them to make informed decisions on resource allocation. Some key considerations for effective resource allocation include:

4.1.4. Time constraint—Time constraints can pose challenges in conducting a thorough TNA. However, with proper planning and effective utilization of available time, educational institutions can still gain valuable insights into teachers' training needs. These experiences implied that principals should choose data collection methods that are cost and time-efficient yet comprehensive, such as targeted surveys, focused interviews, or observation protocols that capture essential information within a limited timeframe. Training needs assessment can help build trust, transparency, and a sense of shared responsibility among teachers and administrators, leading to more effective collaboration and communication. Also, the ineffective use of time and resources may lead to missed opportunities and a lack of progress in addressing teachers' needs, affecting the students' outcomes. Three themes emerged from the school principals' coping strategies: fostering collaboration,

utilizing different assessment techniques, and promoting internal resources.

4.1.5. Fostering collaboration—Collaboration among teachers and educational stakeholders is vital for conducting a successful training needs assessment. By involving multiple perspectives and expertise, collaboration enriches the assessment process and generates valuable insights.

4.1.6. Utilizing different assessment techniques—This ensures a comprehensive understanding of teachers' training needs. Employing a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods provides a well-rounded view of the challenges and areas for improvement.

4.1.7. Promoting internal resources—Leveraging internal resources, such as experienced teachers, instructional coaches, and subject specialists, is a cost-effective and valuable approach to conducting a training needs analysis. Internal resources can provide expertise, mentorship, and support to address identified training needs. These themes implied that organizations could develop more effective, practical, and relevant training programs, build a continuous learning and development culture, and demonstrate their commitment to investing in their employees by adopting these practices. Lastly, in the educational management insights drawn, three themes emerged: conducting program evaluation to measure training effectiveness, involving teachers in the process, and encouraging teacher-led initiatives.

4.1.8. Conducting program evaluations to measure training effectiveness—Program evaluation is a systematic process that assesses a training program's impact, outcomes, and effectiveness. Evaluating teacher training initiatives provides valuable insights into their success, areas of improvement, and overall impact on teacher development.

4.1.9. Involving teachers in the process—Involving teachers in the program evaluation process is vital for obtaining accurate and com-

prehensive insights. When teachers participate in the evaluation, they become active stakeholders, contributing their perspectives and experiences.

4.1.10. *Encouraging teacher-led initiatives*—Empowering teachers to conduct the training actively needs assessment creates a culture of collaboration, professionalism, and continuous development. The themes implied that school principals should conduct training needs analysis with a democratic approach. The efficacy of the training should be determined, and teachers should be assigned roles and responsibilities so that they can take ownership, direction, and responsibility for their own professional development.

4.2. *Future Directions*—This research provides important empirical, theoretical, and practical contributions to investigate the experiences of school principals in training needs analysis for the teachers. Data obtained had directions for various educational stakeholders, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers. The future directions of this study are as follows:

For Policymakers – To devise policies that strengthen school principals’ professional development strategies. The policy should specify what school principals should know, be able to do, and value to conduct Training Needs Analysis for their teachers with competence. They must pay close attention to how they can enhance and maximize the school principals’ abilities to process the volume of information that the Training Needs Analysis provides.

School Principals – They should participate in training to enhance their knowledge and skills in training needs analysis for teachers. This includes improving their democratic leadership by permitting teachers to freely participate in data collection, analysis, exchange of ideas, and discussing how to enhance teacher competence.

Teachers – They should be equipped with ample knowledge of training needs analysis to analyze and make suggestions for designing their training courses, enabling them to work more effectively and boost their morale.

For Future Researchers – It is recommended to consider the involvement of participants from various ranges. As a suggestion, future research should also explore the experiences of Master Teachers in training needs analysis of teachers, anchoring on their specific responsibility, which is to provide individual support and planning small group discussions or training as their technical assistance for teachers. By involving Master Teachers as participants, the study about training needs analysis becomes more significant since it involves many variables to work with. The experiences of Master Teachers could be viewed from different perspectives, such as years of experience in the position and knowledge of training needs analysis. Other than that, it is also suggested that future research could employ more. Future studies could also employ experimental research to see whether using digital tools in learning vocabulary is effective for students or not.

5. References

- Aglazor, G. (2017). The role of teaching practice in teacher education programs: Designing a framework for best practice. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 16(2), 101. <https://doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v16i2.4>
- Aguinis, H., & Kraiger, K. (2009). Research trends in staff development and in-service education. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 13(1), 3–11.
- Amisano. (2010). *The meaning of educational change*. Teachers College Press.

- Anderson, R. (2008). Implications of the information and knowledge society for education. In *International handbook of information technology in primary and secondary education* (pp. 3–22, Vol. 20). https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-0-387-73315-9_1
- Armstrong. (2011). Teacher education psychology of behavior change: Self-confrontation reviewed. *Review of Educational Research*, 469–528.
- Bandon. (2015). *Training in organizations: Needs assessment, development, and evaluation* (4th). Wardsworth.
- Bank. (2018, March). The role of practicum in bridging the gap between school and university [Paper presented at the conference of the Western Canadian Association for Student Teaching].
- Barnard. (1900). *Adolescent problems and design of multiphasic intervention*.
- Barrington. (2007). *Understanding occupational and organizational psychology*. Sage Publications.
- Becker. (1964). *The facilitator pocketbook*. Research press business book.
- Berger & Karn. (2010). *Human resource management* (3rd). Rex Publishing Inc.
- Berkey. (2013). *Teachers' professional development: Europe in international comparison: An analysis of teachers' professional development based on the oecd's teaching and learning international survey (talís)*. European Union.
- Blanchard, P. N., & Thacker, J. W. (2013). *Practical training: Systems, strategies, and practices*. Pearson Higher Ed.
- Bowra, A., et al. (2011). School-level predictors for the use of ict in schools and students' cil in international comparison. *Extensive Scale Assessments in Education*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40536-017-0037-7>
- Brinkerhoff & Gill. (2000). *Evaluating professional development*. Corwin Press, Inc.
- Brown. (2002). Global perspectives: Innovative technology integration practices from around the world. *Learning and Leading with Technology*, 31(2), 7–54.
- Carle, A., Jaffee, D., & Miller, D. (2009). Engaging college science students and changing academic achievements with technology: A quasi-experimental preliminary investigation. *Computers Education*, 52(2), 376–380.
- Carr, N. (2012). The crisis in higher education. *Technology Review*, 115(6), 32–40.
- Clark. (1995). *Creating effective teaching and learning effectiveness*. OECD Publishing.
- Colman. (2012). Designing video games to improve students' motivation. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 31, 571–579.
- Commercemates. (2022). What is training: Types, methods, importance. <https://commercemates.com/what-is-training-types-methods-importance/>
- Corpuz, C. (2013). *Human resource management* (3rd). Rex Publishing Inc.
- Corpuz, C. (2019). Training needs assessment of teachers: The case of de la salle university dasmarinas.
- Corsel. (2013). *Psychometric theory*. McGraw Hill.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). Effective teacher professional development. <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/product/effective-teacher-professionaldevelopment-20ment-brief>
- Doughty & Romiszowski. (2000). *A teachers' guide to talís 2013: Teaching and learning international survey*. OECD Publishing.

- Drossel, K., & Eickelmann, B. (2017). Teachers' participation in professional development concerning the implementation of new technologies in class: A latent class analysis. *Large-scale Assessments in Education*. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s40536-017-0053-7>
- Eickelman, B. (2011). Supportive and hindering factors to a sustainable implementation of ict in schools. *Journal for Educational Research Online*, 3(1), 75–103. https://www.pedocs.de/volltexte/2011/4683/pdf/JERO_2011_1_Eickelmann_Supportive_and_hindering_factors%20_S75_D_A.pdf
- et al., M. (2011). *Considerations for delivery of online professional development for childcare professionals* [Doctoral dissertation, ProQuest Digital Dissertations] [(AAT 3275939)].
- et al., O. (2013). Training needs of teachers in school-based assessment in anglophone west african countries. www.iaea.info/documents/paper_2fb24ab5.pdf
- et al., S. (2010). Investigating barriers teachers face in the implementation of distance education in high schools in gege branch of swaziland. *African Journal of Disability*, 7(10). <https://www.ajod.org>
- European Commission. (2010). *Teachers' professional development: Europe in international comparison: An analysis of teachers' professional development based on the oecd's teaching and learning international survey (talís)*. European Union.
- ExploreHr. (2017). Exploring hr management. <http://www.exploreHR.org/>
- Frailon, J., Ainley, J., Schulz, W., Friedman, T., & Gebhardt, E. (2014). Preparing for life in a digital age: The iea international computer and information literacy study international report. http://www.iea.nl/fileadmin/user_upload/Publications/Electronic_versions/ICILS_2013_International_Report.pdf
- Gerick, J., Eickelmann, B., & Bos, W. (2017). School-level predictors for the use of ict in schools and students' cil in international comparison. *Extensive Scale Assessments in Education*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40536-017-0037-7>
- Gomez-Meija, L. R., Balkin, D. B., & Cardy, R. L. (2001). Developing technology needs assessments for educational programs: An analysis of eight key indicators. *IJEDICT*, 12, 129–143.
- Griswold, D. E., & Boone, R. (2018). Supporting teacher professional development through training needs assessments. *Journal of Human Resources Education*, 12(3), 31–44.
- Gröschner, A., Schindler, A. K., Holzberger, D., Alles, M., & Seidel, T. (2018). How systematic video reflection in teacher professional development regarding classroom discourse contributes to teacher and student self-efficacy. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 90, 223–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2018.02.003>
- Guskey, T. R. (2000). *Evaluating professional development*. Corwin Press, Inc.
- Herzberg. (1950). Getting inside the black box of technology integration in education: Teachers' stimulated recall of classroom observations. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 29(3), 134–144.
- Holton, E. F., Bates, R. A., & Naquin, S. S. (2009). Large-scale performance-driven training needs assessment: A case study. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 21(2), 35–53.
- Holzberger, D., & Prestele, E. (2021). Teacher self-efficacy and self-reported cognitive activation and classroom management: A multilevel perspective on the role of school characteristics. *Learning and Instruction*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2021.101513>

- Idris, N., & Nor, N. (2010). Mathematical creativity: Usage of technology. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2), 1963–1967.
- Ingersoll, R. (2003). Is there a teacher shortage? <http://depts.washington.edu/ctpmail/PDFs/Shortage-RI-09-2003.pdf>
- Kassaw, M. (2022). Measuring of training effectiveness (tref).
- Kercher. (2000). *Information and communication technologies in teacher education: A planning guide*. UNESCO, Division of Higher Education.
- Khan. (2010). Teachers' professional development: A content analysis about the tendencies in studies. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 4(6).
- Khandakar & Sharma. (2005). *Factors related to the pursuance of professional development by elementary school teachers* [Doctoral dissertation, ProQuest Digital Dissertations] [(AAT 3179256)].
- Kirkpatrick. (1975). *Project learning tree: Prek-8 environmental education activity guide*. American Forest Foundation.
- Kozma, R. (2003). Global perspectives: Innovative technology integration practices from around the world. *Learning and Leading with Technology*, 31(2), 7–54.
- Lamboy, C. (2009). Faculty development needs assessment: Report on findings. <https://my.laureate.net/Faculty/docs/Faculty%20Documents/Needs-Assessment-Report-1-09.pdf>
- Liberman. (2005). How society can foster self-directed learning. *Human Development*, 49, 225–228.
- Mack. (2005). *Developing teachers: The challenges of lifelong learning*. Falmer.
- Marketbusinessnews. (2023). Training. <https://marketbusinessnews.com/financial-glossary/training/>
- Matilda. (2011). A program-wide model of positive behavior support in early childhood settings. *Journal of Early Intervention*, 29, 337.
- Maxfield. (2012). *Teaching in america: Opportunity challenge*. National Council for Accreditation of Teacher Education.
- McGhee. (2011). Distance learning [[Pamphlet]].
- Merton. (2011). *Environmental education activity guide*. American Forest Foundation.
- Meyer. (2014). High-quality professional development: Title ix of elementary and secondary education act 2001.
- Miner. (2017). *Critical issues in professional development*. Brookes.
- Mulyata. (2011). Alumni's competencies and user satisfaction of primary teacher training department, faculty of teacher training and education, satyawacana christian university. *Journal SCHOLARIA*, 1(2).
- Nunally, J. (1978). *Psychometric theory*. McGraw Hill.
- OECD. (2009). *Creating effective teaching and learning effectiveness*.
- OECD. (2014). *A teachers' guide to talis 2013: Teaching and learning international survey*.
- Ogba. (2009). Workshop on policy imperatives and teacher competency for inclusive education.
- Olaniyan, D., & Lucas, B. (2008). Teacher preparation for inclusive education: Increasing knowledge but raising concerns. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 39(1), 17–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359866X.2010.540850>
- Olivas. (2007). Closing the trained teacher gap. www.campaignforeducation.org/docs/reports/ECNAT%20Repot_RGBpdf.p3

- O'Reilly, E. (2016). Developing technology needs assessments for educational programs: An analysis of eight key indicators. *IJEDICT*, 12, 129–143.
- Orrill, C. (2006). What does learner-centered professional development look like? *The Mathematics Educator*, 16(1), 4–13.
- Pan. (2008). Role perceptions of school administration team members concerning inclusion of children with disabilities in elementary general schools in israel. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/136031162014.906666>
- Parry. (2000). *Teacher training: Comparison between the context of england and thailand* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Roehampton]. <https://www.roehampton.ac.uk/>
- Purcell. (2008). *Guideline for inclusive education: Ensuring access to education for all*. UNESCO.
- Putri, A. F., Andringrum, H., Rofiah, S. K., & Gunawan, I. (2019). Teacher function in class: A literature review. *International Conference on Education and Training (ICET)*, 382, 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icet-19.2019.2>
- Ribeiro, S. (2020). The real benefits of team collaboration in the workplace. <https://blog.flock.com/benefits-team-collaboration-work#:~:text=Collaboration%20improves%20the%20way%20your,each%20other%20reach%20your%20goals>
- Rosset. (2000). Youth and skills: Putting education to work, efa global monitoring 2000. <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0021/002180/218003e.pdf.p3>
- Rubin. (2010). Managing secondary schools' human resources for national transformation in ebonyi state. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (NAEAP)*, 131–147.
- Schein. (2010). *Teaching in america: Opportunity challenge*. National Council for Accreditation of Teacher Education.
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (2011). Toward professional development for teachers grounded in a theory of decision making. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 43, 457–469. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-011-0307-8>
- Schuller. (2000). Assessing the effect of prompt feedback as a motivational strategy on students' achievement in secondary school mathematics. *Journal of Educational Research*, 3(4), 371–379.
- Sharmaa, S., et al. (2015). Impact analysis of ict teaching aids used for training and development of employees. *Elsevier Ltd. Academic World Education Center*.
- Sims. (2002). Workshop on policy imperatives and teacher competency for inclusive education.
- Smilber. (2011). Assessing the effect of prompt feedback as a motivational strategy on students' achievement in secondary school mathematics. *Journal of Educational Research*, 3(4), 371–379.
- Steadham. (2003). The new teacher: A panacea for effective implementation of inclusive education curriculum in nigeria's school system. *Nigeria Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 18(2), 191–200.
- Stephen & Jones. (2011). The progress of education in south africa: Teachers' experience in a selected district. *Improving Schools*, 14(1), 4–14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1365480210390082>
- Swamson. (2009). *Information and communication technologies in teacher education: A planning guide*. UNESCO, Division of Higher Education.

- Tharenou, A., & Celia. (2007). Extent of implementation of continuous assessment practice by teachers in senior secondary schools. *African Journal of Science Technology Mathematics Education*, 2(1), 72–78.
- Thyers. (2004). *A survey of teacher attitude regarding training within urban school district* [Doctoral dissertation, Philadelphia College of Education].
- Tobey. (2015). Review of needs and development of needs 2.
- Tondeur, J., Kershaw, L., Vanderlinde, R., & Van Braak, J. (2013). Getting inside the black box of technology integration in education: Teachers' stimulated recall of classroom observations. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 29(3), 134–144.
- Tulsian & Pandey. (2009). Workshop on policy imperatives and teacher competency for inclusive education.
- UNESCO. (2009). *Information and communication technologies in teacher education: A planning guide*.
- UNESCO. (2013). *Ict competency standards for teachers: Ict in education teachers' professional development toolkit*.
- Watkins. (2011). Teacher preparation: Increasing knowledge but raising concerns. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 39(1), 17–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359866X.2010.540850>
- Western Michigan University. (2015). Office of the faculty development needs assessment report 2015. <https://wmich.edu/sites/default/files/attachments/u665/2016/OFD%20Needs%20Assessment%202015.pdf>
- Yurtseven, N., & Bademcioglu, M. (2016). Teachers' professional development: A content analysis about the tendencies in studies. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 4(6).